

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING POWERPOINT IN TEACHING ENGLISH: A SURVEY ON HUFU STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

English is considered as an important factor for those who hope to get achievement in the global world. Hence, educators have always been thinking of methodologies, and techniques aiming to help learners find it interesting in learning English so as to be easier in mastering English language skills. With the development of IT, in the passing years, the software of PowerPoint has been encouraged in teaching English. This can help create an impressive teaching and learning environment, and save time. However, whether this application can bring effectiveness or not is still a question that needs to put into consideration. Via a survey on HUFU students' performance in learning English with the assistance of the software of PowerPoint, the finding is that not all cases does the application of using PowerPoint in teaching English bring positive effectiveness. Without a good preparation and a combination of various methodologies, the application may cause unavoidable negative effectiveness.

Key words: Teaching English via PowerPoint, Effectiveness of using PowerPoint in teaching, Teaching and learning English.

1 INTRODUCTION

It cannot be denied that English plays an important role in modern society. English is a means of communication, a common language used in most international conferences, a popular language spoken in many countries all over the world. Teaching and learning English have also become essential in Vietnam in recent years because English is one of the factors that helps Vietnam get closer to the global world. The questions should be raised "How should English be effectively taught so as to help Vietnamese learners easily improve language skills?" To find the answers for the question above, many methodologies and techniques have been applied. Recently, with the development of Information Technology (IT), many software, especially Microsoft Office with PowerPoint, are encouraged to use in teaching and learning English in Vietnam. The reason is that with the help of PowerPoint, an impressive environment of teaching and learning English can be created; teachers and learners can also shorten the time of mastering English skills. However, whether this application can bring effectiveness or not is still a question that needs to put into consideration.

As a common tendency in Vietnam, Ho Chi Minh University of Food Industry (HUFU) has encouraged lecturers to maximize application of PowerPoint in teaching, especially teaching

English. It is the fact that, to some extents, the application of PowerPoint can help learners get more knowledge of English with vivid designs of lessons, and lecturers seem to have more time for activities in class. However, learners seem to make more mistakes in spelling and grammar, and fail to remember vocabularies.

To solve this problem, a survey on HUFU students' performance in learning English with the assistance of the software of PowerPoint is conducted. This study aims at answering the two following questions:

To what extent does the application of PowerPoint bring benefits to learners of English?

What should lecturers of English do to maximize the effectiveness of PowerPoint in teaching English?

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Education technology offers practical applications for educational resources, teaching strategies, transferring information, content determination, and interaction (Muhlise, 2017). Technology-enhanced learning which involves web-based technologies, mobile devices, computers, tablets, and other digital devices (Kirkwood and Price, 2014) can create collaborative learning environment (Marusic and Slisko, 2012) and offers students different ways for communicating with classmates and teachers by providing access to interactive and multimedia content (Bayne, 2015; Conole, 2013). Moreover, in language teaching, technology can also help foster cross-cultural awareness, improve language skills, and increase motivation (Chun, Smith, and Kern, 2016).

Among technologies applied in teaching, Powerpoint have become one of the most popular one, especially in Vietnam. According to Farkas (2006), Powerpoint can be considered as a combination of text, graphics, explanations and advanced features, to engage with the audience.

Powerpoint brings a lot of benefits to learners. First, learners can be concurrently exposed to various forms of visually organized information (Stein, 2006). Second, Powerpoint can help display effective and appropriate written material; leacturers can also deliver slides before the class, which can help learners comprehend the lecture notes on their own which leads to self-study (Mottley, 2003). Third, Powerpoint lectures can help English as a Foreign Language student-teachers easily comprehend the main concepts and theories of teaching and increase their achievement level (Alkash and Al-Dersi, 2013). Susskind (2008) also focused on the positive effects of Powerpoint on developing self-efficacy but without any effect on academic achievement. Last but not least, Powerpoint can make lecturers more motivated (Chigona and Davids, 2014).

Everything has two facets, and Powerpoint may be not an exception. Various drawbacks can also be found in the application of Powerpoint. First, Powerpoint slides may force the teacher to read the slides without providing any opinion or explanation on the issue; slides sometimes contain irrelevant information, which could create confusion or even distract students from the central information; and the given input can submissively be perceived and internalised by students (Muhlise, 2017). Second, Savoy, Proctor, and Salvendy (2009) emphasised the negative effects of

Powerpoint instruction on information retention and asserted that student-generated orality seems to have been downgraded by the unidirectional nature of the discourse which accompanies most Powerpoint. Third, Powerpoint slides are often devoid of paragraphs, pronouns, punctuation, conjunctions, auxiliary verbs and articles (Craig and Amernic, 2006). This may not encourage learners to improve language skills. What is more, Apperson, Laws, and Scepanisky (2008) concluded that students displayed poor performance as a result of the Powerpoint instruction but high preference for being instructed through Powerpoint. Last but not least, Xingeng and Jianxiang (2012) stressed the disadvantages of Powerpoint and expressed that lectures by means of Powerpoint neglected interaction with students and makes a lecture monologue, for the strict order of slides may limit the extemporaneous performance of the instructor.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Participants

The participants of this study consisted of 100 non-major English students in two classes, each of which included 50 students. All the participants were following compulsory English courses in HUFU Foreign Language Center. At the time gathering the data for this study, they were in the second semester of the first year. They all passed the final test of the first English course (A1) in the first semester, and continued the second English course (A2) in the second semester.

As it is defined by Vietnam Ministry of Education, completing A2 level, these participants can understand and use English language structures to listen, read, speak and write about topics related to daily life, such as self-introduction, job and career, family, shopping, hobbies and habits, etc.

As it is designed by HUFU Foreign Language Center, these participants must study the book named “Life” by John Hughes, published by National Geographic Learning, printed in Vietnam in 2017. This book is for A1 and A2 level. A1 level learners study from Unit 1 to Unit 6 of the book, and A2 level learners study from Unit 7 to Unit 12 of the book. There are 3 credits with 45 periods for each level. Learners are tested all four skills: speaking with foreign lecturers in class, listening with Vietnamese lecturers in class, and other skills in final test. Learners must get the average core of 5 to pass the level.

3.2 Instruments

The instrument of this survey is a test designed to figure out students’ performance in three skills, including listening, reading, and writing. The contents of the test are topics in three units 7, 8, 9 of the compulsory materials, which can be found in the Appendix.

Listening and reading are tested with two kinds of questions: Multiple choice and Gap-filling. Writing is tested with Multiple choice and a short paragraph writing.

The purpose of Multiple choice questions is to figure out whether students can absorb main contents of units they studied or not. Gap-filling questions and writing a short paragraph are aimed at students’ ability of memorizing new words and grammar points.

The test is limited to 60 minutes. Each part of the test is given maximum to 10 points. The maximum score for the whole test is 60 points.

The range of points used for later analysis is divided into four groups: 0-4.9 (below average), 5-6.9 (average), 7-8.9 (good), 9-10 (excellent).

3.3 Data collection procedures

In order to figure out whether the application of PowerPoint brings any effectiveness on teaching English or not, steps of conducting survey were done as follows:

First, during 20 periods of the course, two classes called class A and class B were taught with various techniques:

Class A was taught with the assistance of PowerPoint. All the materials were designed via PowerPoint, not except for tasks. Students in this class had a chance to study vocabulary, grammar, skills designed via PowerPoint. After tasks were given, students were required to write the answers on black board; then, the lecturer showed the answers on slides, gave feedbacks to these answers by contrasting the answers on board and those on slides.

Class B was taught via conventional lectures, with chalk and board. The lecturer taught and gave explanation by writing on board and explanations without the usage of PowerPoint. After tasks were given, students were also required to write the answers on black board; then, the lecturer used colored chalks to directly correct the answers on board with explanation.

Second, after finishing three units in the book, including Unit 7, 8, 9, students in two classes are given a task about 60 minutes, testing three skills of listening, reading, and writing. The contents of the test included topics in Unit 7, 8, 9, as described in *Instruments*.

Third, collected data would be transformed into percentage; then, sum of data in number and in percentage would be made in order to be effectively analyzed later.

4 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Findings from test results of Class A

As it is stated above, during the first twenty periods, class A was taught with the assistance of Microsoft PowerPoint. Data collected from the test results of class A can be found in Table 1.

Under multiple choice questions, the number of students getting good and excellent points (7 – 10) is high, accounting for 66% on listening, 60% on reading, and 58% on writing; the number of students getting below average points (0 – 4.9) is low, accounting for only 10% on listening, 12% on reading, and 8% on writing

In contrast, under gap filling questions and short paragraph writing, the number of students getting below average points is very high, accounting for 44% on listening, 40% on reading, and 48% on writing; the number of students getting good and excellent points (7 – 10) is not so high, only 30% on listening, 36% on reading, and 22% on writing.

Of all three tested skills, the number of students getting below average points in writing is the highest, accounting for 48%, and there is no students getting the excellent point.

The number of students getting average points in three skills ranges from 24% to 34%. Of all three tested skills, the number of students getting average points in writing is the highest, accounting for 34% on multiple choice question and 30% on short paragraph writing.

Table 1: Test Results of Class A

	LISTENING		READING		WRITING	
	Multiple Choice	Gap Filling	Multiple Choice	Gap Filling	Multiple Choice	Writing
0 – 4.9 (Below Average)	5 (10%)	22 (44%)	6 (12%)	20 (40%)	4 (8%)	24 (48%)
5 – 6.9 (Average)	12 (24%)	13 (26%)	14 (28%)	12 (24%)	17 (34%)	15 (30%)
7 – 8.9 (Good)	20 (40%)	11 (22%)	18 (36%)	12 (24%)	21 (42%)	11 (22%)
9 – 10 (Excellent)	13 (26%)	4 (8%)	12 (24%)	6 (12%)	8 (16%)	0 (0%)
Total	50 (100%)	50 (100%)	50 (100%)	50 (100%)	50 (100%)	50 (100%)

4.2 Findings from test results of Class B

Different from class A, during the first twenty periods, class B was taught without the assistance of Microsoft PowerPoint; instead, class B was taught with the conventional lecture via board and chalk. Data collected from the test results of class B can be found in Table 2.

Table 2: Test Results of Class B

	LISTENING		READING		WRITING	
	Multiple Choice	Gap Filling	Multiple Choice	Gap Filling	Multiple Choice	Writing
0 – 4 (Below Average)	6 (12%)	11 (22%)	5 (10%)	10 (20%)	5 (10%)	11 (22%)
5 – 6 (Average)	14 (28%)	17 (34%)	13 (26%)	9 (18%)	11 (22%)	17 (34%)

	LISTENING		READING		WRITING	
	Multiple Choice	Gap Filling	Multiple Choice	Gap Filling	Multiple Choice	Writing
7 – 8 (Good)	19 (38%)	12 (24%)	18 (36%)	17 (34%)	24 (48%)	20 (40%)
9 – 10 (Excellent)	11 (22%)	10 (20%)	14 (28%)	14 (28%)	10 (20%)	2 (4%)
Total	50 (100%)	50 (100%)	50 (100%)	50 (100%)	50 (100%)	50 (100%)

Under multiple choice questions, the number of students getting good and excellent points (7 – 10) is high, accounting for 60% on listening, 64% on reading, and 68% on writing; the number of students getting below average points (0 – 4.9) is low, accounting for only 12% on listening, 10% on reading, and 10% on writing

However, different from class A, class B seems to do better on gap filling questions and short paragraph writing. The number of students getting good and excellent points (7 – 10) is also high, accounting for 44% on listening, 62% on reading, and 44% on writing; the number of students in class B receiving below average points, compared to that of class A, is less, accounting for only 30% on listening, 20% on reading, and 22% on writing.

The number of students getting average points in three skills ranges from 22% to 34%, nearly the same as those found in class A. Of all three tested skills, the number of students getting average points in listening is the highest, accounting for 28% on multiple choice question and 34% on gap filling question.

4.3 Discussion

Via the results found in Table 1 and Table 2, it is clearly seen that techniques used in teaching may put impact on students' performance. The following parts will discuss impact of using PowerPoint on students' test performance.

4.3.1 Listening skill

From the results found in the two charts in figure 1, it can be seen that class A and class B have nearly similar score on Multiple choice Listening test. This result ensures that both conventional lecture and technique of PowerPoint can help learners improve English listening skill. The number of students not passing this multiple choice listening test is low, only accounting for 10% - 12%. With the application of PowerPoint, it seems that students getting good and excellent scores are in larger percentage, accounting for 66% compared to 60% found in conventional lecture of board and chalk.

Figure 1: Comparison of multiple choice listening test score

Although the two techniques can help students improve listening skill as found in Figure 1, it seems that the application of PowerPoint cannot help students much in listening gap filling test. This can be proved by higher percentage of students getting below average points in class A, compared to that in class B. Moreover, the percentage of students getting good and excellent points in class A is also 12% higher than that in class B. During the marking process, it is indicated that most of the students in class A failed to write the correct words although from what they write, it is true that they know the words. This can help to come to a conclusion that compared to conventional lecture of board and chalk, PowerPoint fails to help students memorize the spelling of new words; students seem to ignore new word spelling in class, causing the misspelling of the words in listening gap filling test. Via this finding, lecturer should pay attention to techniques of teaching and learning new vocabularies in class so as to help students write the new words accurately.

Figure 2: Comparison of gap filling listening test score

4.3.2 Reading

Similar to listening skill, the two techniques can help students improve reading skill. Under multiple choice reading test, the percentage of students failing the test only accounts for 12% in class A and 10% in class B whereas the percentage of those who get high score, from 7 – 10, is

high in both class: 60% in class A and 64% in class B. Nearly a quarter of the participants in both class reaches the excellent score. This proves that not only lectures with the usage of Powerpoint but also conventional lectures can help students understand contents of the given text.

Figure 3: Comparison of multiple choice reading test score

Figure 4: Comparison of gap filling reading test score

Different from multiple choice reading test, lectures with the usage of Powerpoint cannot help students much in achieving good results. This is proved by 40% of students in class A failing the test. Although initial letters of the words are given aiming to help students remember the words, most of the students in class A cannot fill the gaps with correct words. However, students in class B seems to get better results, with only 20% of students getting below average scores, and higher percentage (28%) of students achieving excellent scores compared to those of class B. Via the marking process, it can be seen that students studying with Powerpoint are bad at writing words correctly. Some students seem to know the content of the given test, but cannot complete blanks with correct spelling words.

Once again, a conclusion may be reached that similar to listening, both techniques can help students improve reading skills; however, under the usage of Powerpoint, students do not pay much attention to new words, resulting in not being able to remember spellings of new words.

4.3.3 Writing

Of all language skills, writing is normally believed to be the most difficult skill. In order to produce a good paragraph or essay, students need to have abundance of words, good knowledge of grammar, good ideas, and skillful writing techniques. Hence, number of students getting high scores in this survey is still limited.

Figure 5: Comparison of multiple choice writing test score

About multiple choice writing test, both classes get good results, indicated by the high percentage of students getting good and excellent score in Figure 5: 58% in class A, and 68% in class B. The percentage of students with failing scores is low: only 8% in class A, and 10% in class B. This finding shows that the two techniques can help students distinguish similar structures in English language, which is essential for writing.

Figure 6: Comparison of short paragraph writing test score

Although students in class A can distinguish different structures in English, they cannot produce a good paragraph, resulting in high percentage of failing scores, accounting for 48%. No students in class A can get excellent marks for short paragraph writing. While marking, it can be found that students in class A do not know how to present the ideas in good grammar and good word

choice. Some students cannot produce complete good grammar sentences. All students in this group make spelling mistakes, even daily used words.

In contrast, students in group B are better. Although there are two students getting the excellent scores, the number of students getting good scores is also in high percentage, accounting for 40%. The percentage of failing score is still high (22%) but it is much less than that found in group A.

Once again, it can be seen that compared to conventional lectures, lectures with the usage of Powerpoint cannot help students much in developing writing skills. These students can only know the grammar points, but they cannot understand grammar points clearly so as to produce a good structured paragraph. About new words, similar to the other two skills, students lack of essential new words and cannot write most of the new words correctly.

5 IMPLICATIONS AND CONCLUSION

It is hard to deny the advantages of using technology in teaching as found in Literature Review, but the overuse of technology, in this case the overuse of Powerpoint, cannot help students much in perfectly improving English language skills. With the assistance of Powerpoint, lecturers can save a lot of time in teaching and learning process in class; also, lecturers can attract students by well-designed slides. However, students may become lazy in writing words, causing abundance of misspelling mistakes in doing tests as found in the survey. Of all tests in three skills, including listening, reading, and writing, students studying with the usage of Powerpoint seem to get the general knowledge of each skill. They can perform well in multiple choice tests, which are only aimed at the ability of getting and realizing information. However, students fail to well perform gap filling test and writing short paragraph test when studying with Powerpoint.

Via the survey and in-class observation, some main reasons can be found: (1) Lecturers do not provide enough time for students to practice writing words and making sentences using studied grammatical structures; (2) Students tend to be lazy in studying to memorize new words; (3) Final tests in HUFU tend to be multiple choice tests, causing the ignorance of essence of new words in teaching and learning; (4) A tendency to maximize quantity of lessons, but not put a focus on the quality.

Hence, in order to help students master language skills perfectly, lecturers should balance conventional lectures and lectures with the usage of Powerpoint in teaching. Lecturers should encourage students to study new words, both meaning and spelling as well as usage, via various kinds of tasks. Students are also encouraged to write on board so that common mistakes are more easily recognized and corrected. Due to the burden of studying time, students normally do not have enough time to practice English at home, thus, tasks helping students easily remember words and language structures in class is a need that lecturers should put into consideration.

Although communication skills, including listening and speaking, may be put a more focus on in future working life, a developing of all skill when studying a language cannot be ignored. That students should be taught how to produce a good paragraph in English is also necessary. In order to produce a good one, abundance of words and good grammatical structures are essential.

Therefore, practising new words and grammatical structures should be paid attention in studying English.

To sum up, according to Muhlise (2017), the use of technology cannot be excluded from educational settings; nevertheless, the extent of its facilities should be determined well in advance to enhance the key components of learning. Conceivably, lecturers can focus on the content, since the slides provide guidelines. For students, particularly for visual students, Powerpoint slides may offer more facilities to follow the course, but it may not be suitable for reflective, impulsive, or auditory students. A well-designed Powerpoint lecture may have an impact on short-term memory of students; it may also allow dynamic and innovative lectures in the classroom for taking the attention of students. Moreover, as teachers become more informed about the affordances of the technology, their teaching practice is simultaneously improved by the given technology-in-use. Additionally, a high degree of interaction with students can also be realised during the Powerpoint lecture, if slides are designed with brief notes on the topic instead of writing the full text.

Last but not least, the limitations of this paper fall on the simplicity of statistic methods as well as the lack of conducting survey on speaking skills. Teaching English with the assistance of technology, specifically with Powerpoint, has been become popular in Vietnam. Thus, figuring out the positive sides and negative sides of this usage is important, which can help lecturers improve teaching methods more effectively and flexibly. Thus, a more focus on speaking skill via the usage of Powerpoint should be essential for later researchers.

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APPENDIX: SURVEY TEST

MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY AND TRADE
HO CHI MINH CITY UNIVERSITY OF FOOD INDUSTRY

TEST OF ENGLISH

Time limited to 60 minutes

NO materials are allowed

Name: _____ Student's ID
number: _____

PART I: LISTENING

Question 1: *Listen to the recordings twice and circle ONE correct answer for each question. (10 pts)*

Recording 1:

1. How many people travelled across the Atlantic Ocean in 1620?
A. 112 B. 121 C. 120 D. 102
2. On what date did the Mayflower leave England?
A. Jun 6th B. Sep 6th C. Nov 11th D. Jul 26th
3. On what date did the Mayflower arrive in America?
A. Dec 6th B. Sep 11th C. Nov 11th D. Oct 6th
4. The "New World" used to be the name of _____.
A. England B. Atlantic Ocean C. America D. Mayflower
5. After the journey, how many times did the Mayflower sail across the Atlantic Ocean?
A. Three B. Four C. Five D. Six

Recording 2:

6. In which country were the photos taken?
A. China B. Spain C. America D. England
7. How many children in masks?
A. Three B. Four C. Five D. Six
8. In which season is this special festival held?
A. Spring B. Autumn C. Summer D. Winter
9. What is the relationship of three children in the photo?
A. Cousins B. All brothers C. Brothers and sister D. All sisters
10. Which of the followings didn't the little girl have?
A. Red cheeks B. Blue eyes C. Blonde hair D. Red ribbon

Question 2: Listen to the recordings twice and complete the blanks with the words you hear. (10 pts)

Reinier Gerritsen is one of my (1) _____ photographers. He's from the Netherlands, but you can often see his photos around the world, in (2) _____ and sometimes in galleries. I've got some books by him as well. His photos are very (3) _____. They often show people in their everyday life. This one is on the New York (4) _____. It's early morning so I think most of the people are (5) _____ to work. They're all standing close together, but they aren't talking to each other. Well, on the right, the man and the woman are talking, but the others aren't. The woman in the (6) _____ is reading her book. And in front of her the woman with blonde hair is listening to music. Then the other blonde woman on the (7) _____ is watching her. I'm not sure what she's thinking, but she looks a bit sad. Oh and look at the other woman at the (8) _____. She's looking straight at the photographers. I take the (9) _____ to work every day, but I never think about the other people. I like it because I don't (10) _____ look at people very closely. But Gerritsen does.

Name: _____ Student's ID
number: _____

PART II: READING

Question 1: *Read the following passage carefully and circle ONE correct answer for each question. (10 pts)*

Stanislaw Witkiewicz. Stanislaw Witkiewicz was born in Zakopane. He died in 1939 but you can see his paintings in art galleries in Poland. Many people like Witkiewicz's paintings of people's faces, but I prefer his paintings of nature and landscapes. He painted this one in 1907. It showed the Hinczow Lakes in the Tatra mountains in southern Poland. There are the green fields and the white rocks and I like this painting because the water in the lake is so blue. I want to swim in it.

Ginger Riley Munduwalawala. In the past, Aboriginal people painted pictures of nature and animals on rocks. In parts of Australia, their Rock Art is 30,000 years old. Nowadays, modern aboriginal artists also paint nature. For example, this colorful painting by Ginger Riley Munduwalawala (1937 – 2002) shows hills, rivers, birds and kangaroos.

Andō Hiroshige. Japanese art is famous for landscape paintings. You can often see the sea and sky, and the mountains and trees. Andō Hiroshige worked in the nineteenth century and he's one of Japan's most famous artists. He printed and sold thousands of beautiful prints in his lifetime. However, he was poor when he died.

Damien Hirst. Damien Hirst is the richest artist in England. He is a painter, but he is more famous for art with different animals (living and dead) including a cow, a sheep, and a shark. In one room of a gallery, he put lots of fruit and real butterflies live there. They fly round the heads of the visitors. For some people, he is a genius, but other people disagree. Personally, I like his work, but I prefer his early paintings.

Vicent Van Gogh. Van Gogh made eleven paintings of sunflowers. They were also Van Gogh's favorite paintings because he loved the color yellow. I prefer his other paintings, but many people love his sunflower paintings. They are everywhere. You see them on cards, postcards and T-shirts. Van Gogh died with no money, but in 1987 someone bought the last sunflower painting for \$49 million.

1. What can be the title of the passage above?

- A. Famous artists around the world.
- B. Colorful pictures of the world.
- C. Nature in art.
- D. Mordern art in painting.

2. Which animal is not mentioned in the passage?

- A. Sheep
- B. Kangaroo
- C. Horse
- D. Cow

3. What is the similar thing between Van Gogh and Hiroshige?

- A. They are famous for paintings of flowers.
- B. They were poor when they died.
- C. They are famous Japanese artists.
- D. Their pictures are printed on postcards and T-shirts.

4. What is not sure about Damien Hirst?

- A. He was a genius.
- B. He was a rich artist.
- C. He was famous for art with different animals.
- D. He used to put real butterflies in one room of a gallery.

5. How old was Ginger Riley Munduwalawala when he died?

- A. 67
- B. 65
- C. 69
- D. 72

Question 2: Complete the blanks with appropriate words. (10 pts)

In many countries, tattoos are in (1) fa_____. On TV you can see a famous actor with a picture on her arm or foot, or your favorite (2) mu_____ with a word on his hand. Many sports (3) pe_____ have got them on their necks and backs. In the US, tattoos are very (4) po_____. 40% of Americans aged between 26 and 40 have got a tattoo and 60% of (5) cu_____ in US tattoo shops are women. These people are often professional people like doctors, teachers, and (6) la_____. However, tattoos are not (7) mo_____. In fact, they are old in human (8) hi_____. For example, archaeologists found a human in ice from five thousand years ago. He had 57 tattoos on his back, (9) an_____, legs, knees, and feet. They were used for many different reasons too. In ancient Egypt, people put on tattoos because they were 'beautiful'. But in ancient Rome, tattoos were negative and put on criminals and (10) pr_____. In India, tattoos were religious.

Name: _____ Student's ID
number: _____

PART III: WRITING

Question 1: *Choose ONE correct answer for each question below. (10 pts)*

1. Which sentence below is correct?

- A. Because I was so hungry I stopped at a restaurant.
- B. I was so hungry so I stopped at a restaurant.
- C. I stopped at a restaurant because I was so hungry.
- D. I was so hungry; so I stopped at a restaurant.

2. Johnson is 20 years old. Jack is 25 years old. Jane is 19 years old.

Which sentence below is correct?

- A. Johnson is the younger of the three.
- B. Jack is oldest of the three.
- C. Among three people, Jack is the oldest.
- D. Johnson is older Jane.

3. Jack has lived in Ho Chi Minh city for three years.

Which sentence below is similar in meaning with the given one?

- A. Jack used to live in Ho Chi Minh city for three years.
- B. Three years ago, Ho Chi Minh city was Jack's favorite place.
- C. For three years, Jack came to live in Ho Chi Minh city.
- D. Jack lived in Ho Chi Minh three years ago.

4. Which sentence below is correct?

- A. At the moment, Tom is having a swim by the river.
- B. Tom is having a new laptop now.
- C. Tom is having a lot of good friends.
- D. Tom has a smoke at the moment.

5. Which sentence below is incorrect?

- A. They are going to leave Vietnam next month.
- B. They are celebrating their wedding party next week.
- C. The plane are going to take off at 7:00 next Tuesday.
- D. The film starts at 7:00 tomorrow evening.

Question 2: *In between 100 – 120 words, write a short pararaph about a journey or a place you have ever visited. (10 pts)*
